

DIRECT MODULAR MULTILEVEL CONVERTER WITH SIX BRANCHES FOR FLEXIBLE DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

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Abstract—

This research uses the soft-open-point method to conduct a thorough analysis of the direct modular multilevel converter (direct MMC) found in medium-voltage distribution networks. The direct MMC may still provide bidirectional power flow between two feeders at any power factor, regardless of whether the feeders operate with different nominal voltages, phase-shift angles, or imbalanced voltages. In order to generate multilayer voltage waveforms, share the blocking voltage of the power switches, and function flawlessly, the six branches of the converter are each constructed of full H-bridge cells that are connected in series. Capacitor voltage balance control, efficiency, power-loss mitigation at various operating points, and the converter's capabilities and restrictions are all covered in this article. In addition, a suitable method of control is suggested. Ten H-bridge cells are required for each phase of an 11-kV, 16-MVA direct MMC system. section, the findings of the simulation, and the estimates of the power loss are given. In order to demonstrate how the characteristics converter and control operate in various operational scenarios, like as grid breakdowns, the distribution network mimics the direct MMC.

INTRODUCTION

A combination of greater peak demand from charging electric cars and more distributed generation (DG) means distribution networks will have to be more adaptable to meet future demands. Serious grid issues like as imbalance voltages,

increased peak and fault currents, needless protection activation, and voltage drops or rises in nearby feeders are brought about by integrating these technologies. Because there is no automated control at 11/0.4 kV, where DG and EVs are, and the sole control is a transformer tap-changer at 33/11 kV substations, the current networks are becoming unable to address these issues.

Thus, it's not feasible to handle many feeds simultaneously. Integrating non-conventional renewable sources, DG, and EVs without compromising reliability, power quality, or efficiency necessitates modernising the 11 kV and 400 V distribution networks. A soft-meshed distribution network with power-flow regulation might be achieved by the deployment of active compensation or energy storage systems, the addition of mesh connections to radial feeders, the management of connections between DG and EVs, and the implementation of soft-open points (SOPs). While active compensation has seen extensive application in transmission (FACTS), it is equally applicable to distribution; however, the distribution network's unique needs must be carefully considered. Only the reactive power-flow can be controlled by the static synchronous compensator (STATCOM); it cannot link two feeds. In addition to requiring specific protection, static synchronous series capacitors (SSSCs) have limited control over actual and reactive power flows, cannot prevent the passage of fault currents, and Back-to-back (B2B) converters are the most versatile and powerful option for power-flow-control between two feeds and can manage current. UPFCs have strong power-flow-control but suffer from the same fault isolation issues as SSSCs.

fault, but it requires two fully-rated power converters. The application of power converters on distribution networks is very restricted to cost, footprint, reliability and power losses. Therefore, (direct) power converters seems to be attractive alternative to converter, but has not been extensively analysed for this propose.

1. DIRECT MODULAR MULTILEVEL CONVERTER (MMC)

Fig. 1 illustrates two synchronized three-phase systems (abc and ABC) connected through power converters that control power flow between two systems. These systems represent feeders distribution network, so they have same frequency and usually same nominal voltage and phase. However, in distribution network it is common that feeders present unbalance voltages and in some specific cases phase shift if they are connected to different transformer configurations (feeders from different

Topology The B2B-MMC converter in Fig. 1(a) has half H-bridges, whereas the direct MMC converter in Fig. 1(b) has complete H-bridges but only six arms. The modular design of both converters makes them fault resistant and able to isolate current issues in any feeder. Compared to B2B-MMC, direct MMC uses half as many capacitors and inductors but has the same amount of semiconductors (without the dc-link). More thorough comparisons of control flexibility, voltage blocking current needed for each semiconductor, capacitor and inductor sizes, and power losses are necessary for both topologies. Stable functioning of the direct MMC operating at synchronous operation (50 Hz) requires a constant AC voltage on each arm. As an example, the converter arms that link the phase A bottom feeder to the phases b and c top feeder may be shown in Figure 1(b). Figures 2 and 1 demonstrate that the topology direct MMC converter suggests that the currents between the two feeds are not independent. The converter injects or consumes the identical amount of reactive power in both feeds, resulting in linked reactive power between the two. Also, feeders with unbalanced voltages are a result of linked currents carrying limits; this is because the converter can only compensate for one feeder's imbalance at a time, ignoring the other. These limitations will be highlighted in the last parts and shown in the simulations

Fig. 1. Modular multilevel converters as soft-open-point. (a) Back-to-Back MMC. (b) Direct MMC (Hex-converter).

A. Basic Operation The direct MMC operation is based on current controller per each arm to obtain line reference current, as shown in (1) and Fig. 2. The arm currents i_{Ab} and i_{Ac} operate in concert to generate i

* A with restriction to be at 90° from respective voltages v_{Ab} and v_{Ac}

Therefore, only their magnitudes change according to the reference line current $i * A$

Fig. 2. Phasor diagram of the currents and voltages of arm Ab and Ac under different operation case scenarios. (a) Both system synchronised and balanced. (b) Phase shift ($\Delta\theta = 30^\circ$) between the two systems. (c) System abc with unbalance voltages. (d) Systems of different voltages (11 kV and 6.6 kV). Fig. 2(b) illustrates operation direct MMC when the feeders have a phase shift (e.g., $\Delta\theta = 30^\circ$). Fig. 2(c) shows the operation when the feeder abc has unbalanced voltages and Fig. 2(d) shows the operation when the systems have different nominal voltages (e.g., 11 kV – 6.6 kV). The proposed control therefore can operate between feeders with different nominal voltages, phase-shift

angles and unbalance voltages

B. Power Rating of the Converter The voltage of each arm is equal to the voltage between the lines of the two feeders as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, the arm voltage depends on the nominal voltage of each feeder, the phase shift between them and the interconnection chosen among the lines. The voltage of each arm can be calculated using trigonometry as shown in (9) and it will be different for each arm if the feeders have a phase shift as illustrated in Fig. 2(b). Anyway, the worst case scenario is when the phase shift 60° because one arm blocks twice the line-to-ground voltage of the feeder while the other arm only blocks half (e.g., 18 kV_{peak} and 9 kV_{peak} for feeders

of 11 kV). Therefore, this maximum blocking voltage is similar to the B2B-MMC but only in half of the arms. On the other hand, the direct MMC has to block less voltage than the B2B-MMC if the feeders have different voltages because the B2B dc-link voltage must be rated for the feeder with higher voltage.

2. CONTROL OF THE DIRECT MMC

Arms Ab and Ac, which make up leg A of the converter, are shown in Fig. 3's control block diagram. Step one involves finding the good

sequence angles and voltages of both systems through an enhanced phase-locked loop (EPPL) system [24]. The angle of the system abc (θ_v) is used as reference for the entire control, and the angle of system ABC (θ_V) is required to calculate the phase shift $\Delta\theta$ between the two systems. Then, the reference current $i^* A$ is calculated by the power controller block using the reference active and reactive power P and Q, and the voltages v_D and v_Q as is presented in (2) and (3)

$$i_D^* = \frac{P^* \cdot v_D + Q^* \cdot v_Q}{v_D^2 + v_Q^2} \quad (2)$$

$$i_Q^* = \frac{P^* \cdot v_Q - Q^* \cdot v_D}{v_D^2 + v_Q^2} \quad (3)$$

The reference current $i^* A$ is obtained directly from the current $i^* DQ$, as shown in (4) and (5). The current angle $\phi^* A$ is obtained adding the phase shift ($\Delta\theta$) because the system dq is used as reference.

$$|\vec{I}_A^*| = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} |\vec{I}_{dq}^*| = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} |\vec{I}_{dq}^*| \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_A^* = \phi_{dq}^* = \phi_{dq}^* + \Delta\theta \quad (5)$$

Then, the current magnitude calculator block of leg A uses the line reference vector

$I^* A$ and the arm current angles $\phi^* Ab$ and $\phi^* Ac$ to calculate the magnitudes of

$I^* Ac$ and _____

$I^* Ab$ through (6) and (7). These equations

are a simple geometric relation of the currents vectors _____

I_A , _____

I_{Ab} and _____

I_{Ac} as shown in Fig. 2

$$I_{Ac}^* = I_A^* \frac{\sin(\phi_A^*) - \cos(\phi_A^*) \cdot \tan(\phi_{Ab}^*)}{\sin(\phi_{Ac}^*) - \cos(\phi_{Ac}^*) \cdot \tan(\phi_{Ab}^*)} \quad (6)$$

$$I_{Ab}^* = \frac{I_A^* \cdot \cos(\phi_A^*) - I_{Ac}^* \cdot \cos(\phi_{Ac}^*)}{\cos(\phi_{Ab}^*)} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Control Block diagram of leg A of the direct MMC.

Fig. 4. Controller block of the current angle $\phi^* Ab$

Fig. 5. Proportional-Resonant current controller, individual capacitor voltage balance controller and multilevel modulation for cell i.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

A simulation model of the direct MMC with the proposed control has been realised in Matlab/Simulink using SimPowerSystem toolbox to validate control performance and to calculate the power losses at various operation points and conditions. Table I summarizes the parameters of the 16 MVA direct MMC used as a power-flow controller between two three-phase feeders of 11 kV and 50 Hz. The nominal voltage of each arm was selected to allow operation at worst condition, which is when the systems have phase shift $\Delta\theta = 60^\circ$, causing some arms to have to provide maximum voltage of 18 kV between lines, as is calculated in (10)

$$V_{\max}^{\text{peak}} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \frac{11 \text{ kV}}{\sqrt{3}} = 18 \text{ kV} \quad (10)$$

The converter therefore uses 10 cells (full H-bridges) per arm with capacitors of 6 mF at 1.8 kV and uses IGBTs of 3.3 kV and 1.2 kA (such as ABB part 5SNA1200E330100). The capacitance was selected to obtain a maximum voltage ripple of $\pm 10\%$ in each capacitor. The switching frequency each cell was fixed at 400 Hz because at this frequency good trade-off is achieved between the switching power losses and the THD of current. The direct MMC generates high number voltage states (e.g., 21) at any operation point, so no high-order filters are

required in converter or feeders, only one inductor 5 mH per arm. The converter is connected directly to grid without transformers to reduce cost, footprint and power losses. The gains controllers were tuned manually and gains PI controller are scheduled according to current angle line and respective arm through nonlinear function implemented in a look-up table.

A. Power Losses The power losses were calculated using the curves provided by the manufacturer of the IGBTs and according to the standard BS EN 62751:2014 presented in [25] and [26]. The following power losses were taken into account: (i) IGBT conduction losses; (ii) IGBT turn-on and turn-off switching losses; (iii) diode reverse recovery losses; and (v) diode conduction

losses. These power losses represent the main power loss of the converter and all the losses in the power electronics because snubbers are not required. Other power losses, such as the capacitor losses, the valve

electronic power consumption and other valve conduction losses were not calculated because they are very lower in comparison [27] and depend on detailed considerations in the design and implementation.

Fig. 6. Simulation of the direct MMC under ideal conditions.

Fig. 7. Simulation in arm Ac under ideal conditions.

B. Performance Under Ideal Conditions

The direct MMC was simulated at nominal power (16 MVA) operating with unity power factor (pure active power-flow) and without phase shift between the two feeders ($\Delta\theta = 0^\circ$) and balanced voltages. Fig. 6 shows the simulation results of the feeder voltages, the feeder currents, the voltage of arm Ac and the capacitor voltages of arm Ac. The current of feeder abc is at 180° from

the grid voltage and from the current of feeder ABC. The THD of the current of both feeders is 0.9%. The voltage of the arm Ac has 21 levels generated by the 10 full H-bridges connected in series and it has a peak voltage of 19.5 kV, higher than the selected nominal peak voltage of 18 kV due to the capacitors being overcharged when the arm voltage reaches the peak. The capacitor voltages of arm Ac are balanced and have a maximum ripple lower than $\pm 10\%$

Fig. 8. Simulation of the direct MMC under fault (three-phase short circuit).

C. AC Fault Blocking Capability The direct MMC was simulated under three-phase fault consisting short circuit between each line of feeder ABC and ground between 0.1 and 1.15 seconds (Fig. 8). The voltages are balanced, without phase shift and with lagging $PF = 0.94$. The control detects the

D. Performance Under Dynamic Power

Fig. 9. Simulation results under dynamic operation

fault and activates the fault mode operation to block fault current. Therefore, converter decreases its current to zero until the fault is cleared. The current is decreased or increased in a controlled manner through a rate limiter to prevent an excessive peak of voltage in arm inductors due to high di/dt . After the current has been controlled to zero, all the IGBTs are turned off.

Operation The direct MMC was simulated with dynamic power operation, which consists

reversal of power over period of 0.1 seconds while keeping leading PF = 0.87. Fig. 9 shows the simulations assuming balanced voltages and no phase shift. The active and reactive power are controlled with high accuracy at all times. It is important to note that reactive power is coupled between the two feeders due to ac-to-ac topology and control characteristics, which mean that both sides of the converter generate or consume exactly the same amount of reactive power.

E. Performance Under the Worst Case Conditions The direct MMC was simulated at nominal power (16 MVA) operating with a leading power factor equal to 0.7, a phase shift between feeders ($\Delta\theta = 30^\circ$) and unbalanced voltages of 2.9%, as shown in

F. Fig. 10. According to the British standard, the voltage unbalance limit for systems with a nominal

voltage below 33 kV is 2% for less than one minute and 1.3% for long term [28]. The chosen power factor, in conjunction with this phase shift, represents the worst case scenario for control stability because the reference line current vector overlaps the vector current of one arm, therefore, the line current is provided almost entirely by one converter arm while the other arm works at very low power but with a highly variable current angle to correct any error.

G. Feeders at Different Nominal Voltages (11 kV and 6.6 kV) The direct MMC was simulated between one feeder of 11 kV and other of 6.6 kV, operating with unity power factor, balanced voltages and without phase shift between the two feeders ($\Delta\theta = 0^\circ$), as shown in Fig. 2(d). The power rating of the converter is now 10 MVA because it is limited by the current of the feeder with lower voltage (6.6 kV). Fig. 11 shows the simulation results of the feeder voltages.

Fig. 10. Simulation results under worst conditions.

Fig. 11. Simulation results with systems with different nominal voltages.

CONCLUSION

Combining features of both the matrix converters and the MMC, the direct MMC is an ac-to-ac converter. Compared to the half-bridge MMC, the direct MMC may produce more levels due to its usage of complete H-bridges linked in series. It is very modular and can be scaled to any voltage or power level, much like other MMCs. The number of semiconductors used is identical to that of the back-to-back MMC; but, due to the need of just six arms, it utilises half as many capacitors and coupling inductors. Because of its potential volume benefit over B2B-MMC during retrofitting to substations, the direct MMC may have less modules, module capacitors, and phase inductors. On the other hand, the direct MMC does not have a dc-link, and the currents in the two feeders are not autonomous. No matter the operating conditions, even the most extreme cases of grid voltage imbalance and phase shift between the two feeds, the direct MMC is easy to use and produces reliable results. Achieving excellent performance, however, requires careful selection of the control settings. There is a large range of potential values for the phase shift and feeder voltages that determine the converter's current and voltage ratings. In contrast to B2B-MMC, which requires a greater current rating but a

lower blocking voltage, direct MMC is always the more feasible option. One benefit of direct MMC over B2B-MMC is a much lower blocking voltage; it may also be utilised between feeders with differing voltages (e.g., 11 kV - 6.6 kV). No filters are needed, which boosts efficiency, particularly at low power operation, since the current quality of the converter is good owing to the large number of voltage levels created (e.g., 21). The efficiency of the direct MMC is 97.54% while operating at rated power, unity power factor, and without phase shift. At a frequency of 400 Hz for the PS-PWM carrier, the conduction losses amount to 56% and the switching losses to 44%. Although the switching losses are almost identical to those of the B2B-MMC, the increased current in each arm causes the conduction losses to be greater. But the converter's working principle increases the current in anti-parallel diodes, which have a slightly lower conduction voltage, and decreases the average current carried by the IGBTs, so reducing conduction losses. The conduction losses are almost 68% more than those of the B2B-MMC.

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